

USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PILGRIMAGE TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. Today, the competition between individual countries to attract tourists is increasing all over the world, which leads to the search for new ways of marketing the tourism industry. It also requires research and innovation. Taking this into account, our country pays special attention to this area and not only attracts foreign tourists to our country, but also develops domestic tourism together. Through these works, it is expected not only to increase the flow of tourists, but also to improve the quality of services and achieve results in the fields of modernization.

The use of digital technologies in tourism is the use of digital tools in planning, organizing, controlling and enjoying the trip, a set of electronic services provided to travelers before, during and after the trip. For this reason, more than 95 percent of tourists today plan their trips online and use digital resources during their vacations. This article examines the benefits and importance of digitalization in the tourism industry.

Keywords: pilgrimage tourism, artificial intelligence, green economy, digitalization, Internet, tourist agencies, advertising, social media, marketing, travel, service.

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda butun dunyoda turistlarni jalb qilish uchun alohida mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi raqobat kuchayib bormoqda, bu esa turizm industriyasini marketingning yangi usullarini izlashga olib keladi. Bu ham tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarni talab qiladi. Shuni inobatga olgan holda mamlakatimizda ushbu sohaga alohida e'tibor qaratilib, nafaqat xorijlik sayyohlarni yurtimizga jalb etish, balki ichki turizmni ham birgalikda rivojlantirishga erishilmoqda. Bu ishlar orqali nafaqat sayyohlar oqimini oshirish, balki xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini oshirish, modernizatsiya yo'nalishlarida ham natijalarga erishish kutilmoqda.

Turizmدا raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish - sayohatni rejalashtirish, tashkil etish, nazorat qilish va undan zavqlanishda raqamli vositalardan foydalanish, sayohatchilarga sayohatdan oldin, davomida va undan keyin ko'rsatiladigan elektron xizmatlar to'plami. Shu sababli, bugungi kunda sayyohlarning 95 foizdan ortig'i o'z sayohatlarini onlayn rejalashtirishadi va ta'til paytida raqamli resurslardan foydalanadilar. Ushbu maqola turizm sanoatida raqamlashtirishning afzalliklari va ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ziyorat turizmi, sun'iy intellekt, yashil iqtisodiyot, raqamlashtirish, Internet, sayyohlik agentliklari, reklama, ijtimoiy media, marketing, sayohat, xizmat ko'rsatish.

Аннотация. Сегодня во всем мире усиливается конкуренция между отдельными странами за привлечение туристов, что приводит к поиску новых способов сбыта туристической отрасли. Это также требует исследований и инноваций. Принимая это во внимание, наша страна уделяет этому направлению особое внимание и не только привлекает иностранных туристов в нашу страну, но и вместе развивает внутренний туризм. Благодаря этим работам ожидается не только увеличить поток туристов, но и улучшить качество услуг и добиться результатов в сфере модернизации.

Использование цифровых технологий в туризме – это использование цифровых инструментов при планировании, организации, контроле и получении удовольствия от поездки, набора электронных услуг, предоставляемых путешественникам до, во время и после поездки. По этой причине более 95 процентов туристов сегодня планируют свои

поездки онлайн и используют цифровые ресурсы во время отпуска. В статье рассматриваются преимущества и важность цифровизации в туристической отрасли.

Ключевые слова: *паломнический туризм, искусственный интеллект, зеленая экономика, цифровизация, Интернет, туристические агентства, реклама, социальные сети, маркетинг, путешествия, сервис.*

Digitization offers technologies, approaches and tools that increase the value of the tourism product. The potential of digitalization of business in the field of tourism depends on the financial and technological capabilities of each subject and the industry as a whole. In recent years, the tourism market of Uzbekistan has significantly increased its size. Online booking services in our country have serious growth prospects, while classic travel agencies will also remain available. Tourism is currently one of the largest and most promising sectors of the world economy. It plays an important role in job creation, export earnings of many countries and overall contribution to GDP. Existing political differences, sanctions, regional conflicts, the number of international tourist destinations is steadily growing year by year. The new opportunities that are opening up for a person due to the development of the digital economy are undoubtedly positive changes that open up new opportunities in almost all spheres of activity. With the development of digital technologies, the consumer can receive ordered services faster, as well as save money, because prices on the Internet are often lower than those offered by offline businesses. Through this economical method, travelers will have more options and will be able to find different types of accommodation at affordable prices. Ride-sharing apps are becoming more and more popular these days. Drivers take multiple passengers along the same route, which benefits passengers, drivers and platform owners. Travel companies are increasingly relying on mobile applications for growth. More than 35% of users book travel through mobile apps, and this percentage will soon increase. Developing your mobile app is undoubtedly expensive for several market participants, but it is worth it. Alternatively, many companies are launching and signing up as resellers of other travel apps that save time and money. Travel apps often provide you with the most popular destinations. In 2017-2020, the number of foreign tourists who came to Uzbekistan almost doubled. In 2017, their number was 2.7 million, and in 2022, this figure will reach 5.2 million. In 2022, the number of tourists who came to Uzbekistan exceeded 3.4 million people compared to 2021, and the increase was more than 2.8 times. As a result, there was a significant increase in the export of tourism services.

In 2022, this indicator will increase 2.9 times and reach 1.6 billion. In 2017-2022, the share of export of tourism services in the total volume of export of services increased by 1.8 times. However, tourism is the sector that is developing the economy of the fastest developing countries in the world and brings good income.

In 2021, the growth and development indicators of the economy and the tourism industry in the digital tourism economy of the countries that used digital technologies for the development of tourism were compared. 1-graph (the growth and development indicators of the economy and the tourism industry in the digital tourism economy of the countries in 2021)

Countries	Economical grow(%)	The growth of the digital tourism industry (%)
CHINA	6.5	33.0
USA	6.4	25.0
JAPAN	2.8	20.0
BRAZIL	4.1	22.0
BRITAIN	4.1	15.0
GERMANY	3.6	22.0

New technologies are playing an increasingly important role in enhancing the tourist experience, and many tourism industries are using technology to improve the travel experience for tourists. Such technologies include virtual and augmented reality, robotics and artificial intelligence (AI), and electronic payment systems. A virtual tour allows you to familiarize yourself with tourist attractions through photos and videos before making a trip. Augmented reality can also be used to inform tourists about the space and objects around them.

Blockchain technology can improve the tourism industry by creating transparency in transactions, preventing fraud and data misuse, improving transaction quality and speed, and reducing transaction costs. In addition, the tourism industry can improve the tourism system using digital technologies through artificial intelligence, augmented reality, IoT, electronic payment systems and data analytics, increasing efficiency and productivity and expanding the tourist experience. These technologies allow to provide attractive and interactive experiences for tourists, to improve the planning of the tourism system and to develop the best strategies for attracting tourists.

Complex measures are being implemented in our country for the active development of the digital economy, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and areas, first of all, in public administration, education, health care and agriculture.

In particular, the implementation of more than 220 priority projects aimed at improving the electronic government system, further developing the local market of software products and information technologies, establishing IT parks in all regions of the republic, as well as providing the sector with qualified personnel has begun.

Many travel companies use social media for advertising and marketing by providing practical information, discounts and special offers to their target audience in order to create effective marketing for themselves. Social networks can also serve as a means of communication between tourists and travel companies, and improve the quality of service to tourists. Since social media advertising is cheaper than traditional media, many tourism companies use this method for marketing and advertising.

Social media advertising is especially effective for small businesses, providing an affordable and effective solution to marketing and promoting their services in the digital world. Digitization, digital economy and innovation are interconnected in various economic sectors, including the tourism industry. Using digital technologies, travel companies can easily

communicate with their target audience, provide useful information and offer their services and products to customers online.

These technologies offer a number of advantages, such as increased marketing opportunities, improved customer service, improved tourist experience, efficient use of resources and secure transactions. The use of digital technologies in the field of tourism can increase the efficiency and quality of tourism-related services. Travel websites and applications, electronic booking and payment systems, and providing accurate and up-to-date information to travelers can improve the efficiency and quality of services.

According to the Central Bank, by the end of 2023, the total amount of money received by the banks of Uzbekistan amounted to 669 trillion soums, which is 28% more than in 2022 (522 trillion). Thus, cash receipts to banks increased by 20% in one year and amounted to 414 trillion soums. But despite this, the share of cash has decreased from 66% to 62% (it was 69% in 2021). As for cash receipts received through terminals, they increased by 44% to 255 trillion soums, and their share increased from 34% to 38% (in 2021 - 31%).

The population of almost all countries of the world is active in Internet services used in a way Through this global network, they are completely for themselves the history of unfamiliar countries that he has never seen in his life and a lot of information about today's conditions in a few minutes have the opportunity to collect. This, in turn, is the development of tourism and the country can make a significant contribution to the economy. The field of tourism Using digital transformations for improvement and development is one how many possibilities it opens.

Attracting additional investments in the direction of tourism, further improving tourism infrastructure by creating favorable conditions for the private sector, increasing population employment, expanding transport routes, accelerating the promotion of the republic's tourist potential in domestic and foreign markets, as well as , a number of works were determined by the President in order to introduce new procedures in state management of the sector

The level of tourism development is the socio-economic development of the country, its regions and is one of the parameters describing the well-being of the population. Especially innovations in the field of tourism plays an important role. World practice shows that tourism profitability and development dynamics. It ranks second after oil and gas extraction and processing. There is a lot of tourism for the national economies of the states and is the most important area of economic activity. In addition, tourism is an information-rich industry that involves the collection, transmission, analysis, and storage of information. it should be noted that it plays an important role in decision-making at all levels of the industry. Therefore, the formation and development of the digital economy is important for tourism activities is important, and the latest information and communication technologies are actively used in it.

National online reservation of hotels "MyBooking" system should also be noted. Through this system, tourists can book a room in a few minutes and pay for staying in a hotel. The system is also flexible from VISA and MasterCard cards uses a system of discounts - these factors are non-cash payments stimulates growth. Use of UzCard service and national the ability to accept payments in foreign currency supports domestic tourism serves as a convenient tool for organizing business trips.

It is noted that digital technologies will dramatically change more than 50 percent of the sectors related to the economy. This vision is based on the fact that information technologies and digital platforms will dramatically change business models, eliminate intermediaries and optimize processes for their efficiency. According to the calculations of the World Bank, a 10% increase in

the number of high-speed Internet users can increase the annual GDP from 0.4% to 1.4%. Also, the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP is considered to be an indicator of its importance. In 2010, the Boston Consulting Group estimated the scale of digitalization at \$2.3 trillion (4.1 percent of GDP) for a group of 20 countries. If this trend continues, after 10-15 years the share of such an economy in the world GDP will approach 30-40%

Today, developing societies are rapidly approaching industrialized societies the fourth industrial revolution, which is increasingly penetrating into the organic structure of the economies of countries that the modern form of socio-economic development is expanding "digital economy" means The fact that the digital economy in the world has exceeded 2 trillion US dollars in 20 socio-economically developed countries is a clear proof of this. Including the digital economy in developed Great Britain it reached 12% of national GDP. An important feature of the digital economy is the concept of "smart city" or "creative city" reflects. In this "digital space", people start to live smarter and more intellectually. That's why for intellectual people, inclusive education and lifelong learning in the formation of such a city becomes the main criterion. The social capital of such cities is in an industrialized economic system creates in the creation of the added value chain.

Digitalization is expected to continue propelling the travel experience on its trajectory towards becoming more seamless, frictionless, and high quality and in a way that contributes to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. The use of technologies including the 'Internet of Things', location-based services, artificial intelligence, augmented and virtual reality, and blockchain technology (see definitions below) has resulted in a tourism offer that is more attractive, efficient, inclusive, and economically, socially and environmentally sustainable than its predecessor. It has also facilitated innovation and rethinking of processes, with a view to tackling challenges such as seasonality and overcrowding and developing smarter destinations.

CONCLUSION

Considering the above, we can conclude the external environment of tourism activity the digital economy and the formation of new products listed above in the analysis, great attention to the factors that directly affect the implementation and subsequent development should be focused. All this has a positive effect on the development of the entire tourism industry.

The development of the digital economy affects many types of economic activity, including tourism will significantly change the provision of infrastructure. The basis of the digital economy is large considering that it is the processing of information in the volume, information storage, processing and high-tech transmission system is of particular importance. Convenience to potential tourists purchase of airline tickets, hotel reservations, travel around the region in order to create to do, providing information and ratings about attractions, cultural and historical heritage we should expect the active development of mobile technologies that provide a wide range of functions.

The digital economy has the potential to create new forms of tourism enterprises creates There will be serious changes in the field of personnel infrastructure. Our social life and tourist activities are becoming increasingly technological, world tourism forming a new unified information space in the field of information provision and tourism management system is being developed.

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